

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Profile Studies of Laterite Soils

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Profile studies of Indian soils have mostly been undertaken for their classification¹⁻³ and genesis⁴⁻⁷ and as such, information on the distribution of clay minerals in the different horizons of Indian soils is very meagre. The present investigation has been undertaken with the object of partly filling up this lacuna. The clay fractions ($<2\mu$) isolated from three lateritic soils, viz., Salboni ($S_1, 0-7''$; $S_2, 7-33''$; $S_3, 33-58''$ and $S_4, 58''+$), Kolar ($Kl_1, 0-33''$; $Kl_2, 33-41''$; and $Kl_3, 41''+$) and Hoskote ($Hkt_1, 0-5''$; $Hkt_2, 5-13''$; $Hkt_3, 13-33''$; $Hkt_4, 33-45''$, and $Hkt_5, 45-58''$), were converted into their hydrogen forms (H-clays) by the usual procedures. The clay mineralogical composition of these H-clays has been determined using chemical, electrochemical, X-ray and differential thermal analytical techniques.

The nature and abundance of heavy minerals in the sand fractions have also been determined by petrographic method for obtaining information on the formation and development of these soils. Some of the important results obtained so far have been discussed in this short note. The details will be published in a full paper.

No appreciable illuviation of iron oxide in the Salboni and Kolar profiles is noticed but there is an accumulation of iron oxide in the third horizon of Hoskote profile. The molar SiO_2/Al_2O_3 ratios around 2.0 of these clays indicate their kaolinitic nature. The presence of potassium in the clays suggests that illite may also be present in these clays. As judged from potassium contents, the surface layers of all three profiles seem to contain higher amounts of illite, its contents being in the order, Salboni $>$ Kolar $\approx$ Hoskote.

The potentiometric titration curve with KOH of both Salboni and Kolar H-clays shows three inflexion points, between pH 6.0 and 7.4, pH 8.0 and 9.5 and between pH 10.0 and 10.7 respectively. But that of the Hoskote H-clays shows only two inflexion points, between pH 5.6 and 5.9 and between pH 7.0 and 7.3. The ratio of the total acidities at the first and second inflexion points varies between 1.25 and 2.27, between 1.67 and 2.23 and is close to 2.0 for Salboni, Kolar and Hoskote clays respectively. The ratio between the

1. Ray Choudhuri, *Bull. Natl. Inst. Sci. (India)* 1962, 26, 102.
2. Gobinda Rajan and Datta Biswas, *Bull. Natl. Inst. Sci. (India)* 1962, 26, 117.
3. Wadia, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.* 1960, 8, 5.
4. Satyanarayana, *Bull. Natl. Inst. Sci. (India)* 1962, 26, 84.
5. Ray Choudhuri (1958), *Bull. Indian Coun. Agric. Res.*, No. 73, Final Report of All India Soil Survey Scheme.
6. Murthy, Mathur, Ray Choudhuri (1962), *Proc. Natl. Inst. Sci. India* A28.
7. Srinivasan and Venkatraman, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.* 1960, 8, 35.

second and third inflexion points similarly lies between 1.96 and 2.48 and between 1.91 and 2.11 for Salboni and Kolar clays respectively. The total acidities at the final inflexion points in the titration curves of H-clays with KOH vary between 49.0 and 62.0, 38.0 and 44.0 and 10.00 to 12.0 m.e. per 100 gm. for the Salboni, Kolar and Hoskote clays respectively. The viscosity increases with the gradual addition of KOH to H-clays, and shows maxima between 26.0 and 64.0 percent neutralisation in the case of Salboni clays and between 17 and 50 percent neutralisation in the case of Kolar clays. No such viscosity maximum has been observed with Hoskote clays. An examination of the nature of the potentiometric titration curves, the total acidities calculated at inflexion points in the titration curves, the pH at inflexion points, the ratios of the total acidities at the inflexion points and the nature of the viscosity neutralisation variations suggests that Salboni and Kolar clays are predominantly illitic⁹ but contain varying amounts of kaolinite, while Hoskote clay is mainly kaolinitic¹⁰.

The presence of 7.2 Å lines in the X-ray diffraction picture of Salboni and Kolar clays and lines around 7.1 Å in Hoskote clays suggests that these clays are mainly kaolinitic. Glycerol solvated clays do not show the 18 Å line of montmorillonite. However, the very weak reflections around 10 Å show that Salboni clays contain in addition to kaolinite a small amount of illite. The X-ray data indicate a more or less uniform distribution of clay minerals throughout the profiles.

The D.T.A. data for the clays show two endothermic peaks, one around 140°C and the other around 590°C, and an exothermic peak between 920°C and 960°C, indicating that the dominant clay mineral in these clays is kaolinite but may contain minor amount of illite. The D.T.A. graphs also show a more or less uniform distribution of clay minerals in Salboni and Kolar profiles but an increase of kaolinite down the Hoskote soil profile as seen from the shift of the peak temperatures. A comparison of these data with those for binary mixtures¹¹ of kaolinite and illite suggests that kaolinite may be present in these clays to the extent of 70-80%.

Petrographic analysis shows that the heavy minerals of Kolar soil are mainly constituted of magnetite and ilmenite, and in the light minerals fractions quartz and feldspar are prominent. The heavy minerals in Salboni soil are ilmenite and magnetite and occasional grains of pyroxenes. The Hoskote soil contains pyroxene, ilmenite, limonite as the principal minerals having rutile, chlorite, sphene and tourmaline as the subsidiary minerals.

The country rocks of the Kolar and the Hoskote areas belong to the Archaean group and are of granitic composition, containing in addition hornblende, biotite, pyroxene, spearsartite, sphene and opaque minerals. Among the principal minerals, magnetite, ilmenite and pyroxene are likely to survive the process of weathering and erosion. It is evident therefore that in the soil there should be some concentration of these minerals, as petrographic analysis shows. However, the presence of the subsidiary minerals like rutile, chlorite, sphene, tourmaline suggests their origin from metamorphic Archaean rock. The presence of pyroxene and limonite as principal minerals in Hoskote soil is indicative of its immaturity in comparison to Kolar soil. The nature of the heavy minerals in Salboni soil suggests

8. Mitra and Rajagopalan, *Nature*, Lond., 1948, 162, 104.

9. Mukherjee and Mitra, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1946 1, 141.

10. Sarkar and Chatterjee, *this Journal* 1961a), 33, 725.

its formation from basic igneous rocks. Because of high rainfall and good drainage, the magnesium and potassium have mostly been rapidly leached but in course of weathering, resulting in the formation of kaolinite¹.

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